

NDAC/LO/152

Nov 2, 1994

HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, XX

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This report is about solution experiments made from the 30-month Case History Files, leading to thoroughly revised and improved STDDBL and SEEKDBL programs.

1. 30-month CHF:s

The 'real' 30-month CHF-generation awaited the April -94 photometric reductions from RGO, and they also included (for the first time) the 'constant chromaticity'-corrections. Also, the selection of 'suspected non-singles' (depending heavily on the AC-DC magnitudes) was redone, with rather large consequences.

The selection was made as described in NDAC/LO/149, but with the 'known dbl' category updated using the 940530-version of the PRIORI-catalogue by Pannunzio et al, plus information from Dommanget and Nys (940419). The RGO photometric calibrations were 'improved' for the reddest stars, to have the AC and DC magnitudes approximately equal for the majority (=single stars). With a target number of 'suspected non-singles' about equal to the known doubles, the final categories were as follows: 13412 entries in 12448 'known double systems'(D), 13596 'suspected non-singles'(S), 1246 entries in 1044 'multiple systems'(M) and 5083 'bona-fide singles'(I). Interestingly, almost 2000 former S-systems with double-star solutions were now not even flagged as suspects, but CHF:s were still derived for them for checking purposes. Many of these are red stars selected before because of a bad AC-DC calibrations.

A correction for constant chromaticity was made according to the time-varying (T =years since 1991.25) formula given by Lindegren

$$da = (-1.110 + 0.366 T) * (B_T - V_T - 0.5) \quad \text{mas}$$

(with careful checking of the sign!), using however the approximation $B_T - V_T = 1.15(V - I)$.

Then (June 94) the actual CHF-derivation was made with no particular problems, requiring mainly a careful administration of many passes of data between disk and DAT-tapes, ending up with 389 Mb of Case History Files for further solution experiments. (Actually, some of the more recent experiments described below have used a 37-month CHF-derivation finished on Sept 30, which will be described in a forthcoming Paper XXI).

2. Calibration solutions

The standard solution program SEEKDBL was then used on the (I)-CHF:s, which as expected gave mostly single-star solutions. Comparison with NDAC's sphere solution gave results similar to but slightly better than those in NDAC/LO/149. (The improvement should be due mainly to the chromaticity-corrections). Similarly, the standard comparison of the data for 2-pointing doubles with the sphere solution gave the expected convergence at large effective magnitude differences.

The 'half-observation' covariance-calibrations could now be run for a larger number of solutions. (Because of different practical problems, the final data is

about 6000+6000 STDDBL-solutions). Contrary to the provisional conclusion in NDAC/LO/151, it seems that the covariances need to be multiplied by a factor depending on both S_f and H_p . It is also apparent, however, that especially the 'relative' data can not be fitted very well by a single relation. In September, I worked out compromise calibrations with 'absolute' mean errors multiplied by $0.9\sqrt{S_f}[1 + 0.063 * (H_p - 7)]$, 'relative' ones by $1.2\sqrt{S_f}[1 + 0.11|(H_p - 8)|]$. Later, I have realized that a 'normalizing factor' used to remove a magnitude equation in the S_f :s is in fact almost identical to the 'relative' expression above, thus there may be only a S_f -dependence after all (if the difference between the 'absolute' and 'relative' relations for the (few) bright stars is considered spurious). It seems difficult to avoid some systematic effects at the 20%-level, and maybe a new round of 'half-observations' has to be made from 37-month data. Comparison with the sphere-solution covariances for 'single' stars gives a good agreement for $H_p > 7$, but with a hint that the sphere-solution covariances may be underestimated for the brighter stars.

3. Standard solutions

With most of the solution-programs unchanged since the preliminary 30-month runs in February (and without the above new covariance-calibrations), STDDBL and SEEKDBL were run to give a first reasonably full set of 30-month solutions. With the old cut-offs (5.0 for known, 4.5 for new solutions) in Δm_{eff} , this gave about 9100 known and 6500 new double star solutions, which were communicated to FAST. No full-scale comparisons have been made from these data, but from preliminary work by Francois Mignard, it appears that for most of the objects with solutions in both consortia, the agreement is good in both relative and absolute astrometry. There were rather many objects with solutions in only one of the consortia, however, and the solution programs are thus not yet optimal. Further comparisons are postponed until 37-month solutions are available in both consortia.

4. New solution principles

So far (since preliminary simulations in 1986...), the b_1 (DC component) observations have not been used in NDAC's DS reductions. The original reason was that erroneous colours (influencing the assumed modulation amplitudes) could give incompatible AC and DC intensities, which would then generate systematic errors in the astrometry. Using only the AC-data, all the astrometric information is utilized, but the photometric results (especially for the primary magnitude) have somewhat larger errors than with the DC observations included. This was deemed of no great consequence when the photometry was to be derived separately from the DC data, but some inconsistencies between the astrometry and the photometry are then unavoidable.

A more unified approach is to use in fact all the observations (AC+DC) in the DS reductions, thereby deriving an internally consistent set of astrometric and photometric parameters. Hopefully, the combined (DC-dominated) photometry from these solutions will be close to the standard DC photometry, with a compatible astrometry. The original fear of large colour-effects remains, but it should be possible to flag and investigate all cases with gross AC/DC deviations.

These ideas have been tested in several new versions of SEEKDBL/STDDBL. From these tests it appears clearly advantageous to stick to the old (AC only) procedures in all preliminary mesh-searches, including the use of the standard (b_2 - b_5) normalized fit to the observations (S_f). Then, when an AC solution is obtained, an extra AC+DC (b_1 included) solution is also derived in an extra least squares loop at

the end. This does not always work, but failure usually signifies a real problem with the solution.

For most systems, the AC+DC solution differs little from the AC one. Only if the colour (used in all calibrations) is wrong, there will be systematic position-differences between the two solutions. A first test is again obtained from the comparison with the sphere-solution for 'single' stars. In Table 1 are given such results, and the very slightly 'worse' AC+DC results reflects the fact that the sphere solution (purely astrometric) is in principle equivalent to the AC double-star solution. The difference AC/(AC+DC) is very marginal, however, and are not expected to produce any sensible bias. The last column in Table 1 lists normalized standard deviations about 0.5-0.6, showing that (as expected), the sphere-solution and the DS solution are appreciably correlated.

Table 1. Statistics for the differences between the two DS-solutions (AC, and AC+DC) and the sphere solution results for 'bona fide single' stars in different magnitude-intervals. The absolute differences are given in mas (mas/yr), while the normalized differences (for the AC) solution have been divided by the sphere solution σ .

Parameter	Hp	n	Diff(AC)		Diff(AC+DC)		Norm diff(AC)	
			mean	stddev	mean	stddev	mean	stddev
α	< 7	655	-.05(0.60)		-.05(0.60)		-.04(0.61)	
δ	< 7	655	-.01(0.51)		-.01(0.52)		-.01(0.63)	
π	< 7	655	+.06(0.71)		+.06(0.71)		+.05(0.58)	
μ_α	< 7	655	-.16(0.87)		-.16(0.87)		-.12(0.62)	
μ_δ	< 7	655	.00(0.77)		.00(0.77)		.00(0.67)	
α	7-10	3712	-.07(0.63)		-.07(0.63)		-.06(0.51)	
δ	7-10	3712	-.02(0.56)		-.02(0.56)		-.02(0.53)	
π	7-10	3712	+.05(0.76)		+.05(0.77)		+.04(0.50)	
μ_α	7-10	3712	-.09(0.91)		-.09(0.91)		-.07(0.51)	
μ_δ	7-10	3712	-.04(0.79)		-.04(0.79)		-.03(0.54)	
α	> 10	368	-.02(1.34)		-.02(1.36)		-.01(0.58)	
δ	> 10	368	-.02(1.06)		-.03(1.07)		-.02(0.63)	
π	> 10	368	-.01(1.45)		-.01(1.46)		.00(0.56)	
μ_α	> 10	368	+.06(1.74)		+.06(1.77)		+.03(0.60)	
μ_δ	> 10	368	-.04(1.57)		-.05(1.59)		-.03(0.63)	

A comparison of the AC and AC+DC solutions for double stars can be made in many ways. One measure of the deviation between the two solutions is given by normalized χ^2 parameters, X_1 giving the deviation for the two absolute position parameters, X_2 for the proper motions and the parallax, and X_3 for the relative x,y for the secondary. 'Typical' median values are about 0.02, 0.002 and 0.1 respectively, and values much greater than unity signal a possible problem to be investigated further.

Another weak spot in all my previous program-versions is the rejection of 'outlier' observations. This had been done independently at each mesh-point and for the single and double-star solutions, resulting in S_f -values that did not strictly refer to the same set observations. The selection of the 'best' solution (single or double) was then made on the basis of these S_f :s, which in marginal cases may not have been the optimum choice. (In the great majority of cases, however, the 'obvious' outliers were

correctly identified). To close this unnecessary loophole, I have tried to implement a more well-defined procedure that fixes the rejection to a single set of observations that is kept fixed for all solution trials. Although the decision when to 'freeze' the observations is rather ad hoc, the new program-versions seem to work as well as the old (and hopefully making a better selection of the 'best' solution).

5. Photometry

The new AC+DC solutions give a new photometry to compare to the 'standard' DC one. A first such comparison has been done by Dafydd Evans for the set of 'bona-fide singles' defined above. The systematic differences are below about 0.01 mag and may probably be rather well calibrated mainly as a function of magnitude.

A more difficult question is how the doubles with variable components shall be handled. Even with rather permissive limits (for constancy), a sensible proportion of the stars are variable, and because NDAC's standard solution model assumes constant luminosities, this is a real problem. The method that has been developed to solve it is admittedly not ideal, but it works for a majority of cases. Only for long-period, large-amplitude systems, a more rigorous approach will be necessary, but these are hopefully rather few.

The procedure is simple. First, in order to avoid too many outliers, the original b1-observations are checked and only those observations used that lie within about 25 % from the median. Then, a standard astrometric+photometric solution is derived, using only the AC observations. The astrometric parameters from this solution are then 'fixed', and at each FOVC, a new solution for the photometry (Hp_1 , ΔHp) is made (needing some extra iterations). In these 'photometry only' solutions, the originally discarded outliers may be used, and at each FOVC one gets two magnitudes and their 2x2 covariance matrix. (In some cases, the geometry is bad or the observations poor, and it is not possible to get a reasonable solution. In such cases the secondary magnitude is fixed at its mean value, and only a primary magnitude is derived). The output from this extra procedure is transformed to a list [time, Hp_1 , $\text{sig}(Hp_1)$, Hp_2 , $\text{sig}(Hp_2)$, Hp_{comb} , $\text{sig}(Hp_{\text{comb}})$] for each observed FOVC.

In most cases, there is no significant variability in the data, and then a final AC+DC solution made, with constant Hp_1 , ΔHp assumed. The next level of complication is when the normalized amplitude (here=full distance between the 10 and 90 percentile points for (mag-median)/sigma) in the combined magnitude is significant ($> t_v, t_v \sim 5 - 10$), but when the individual Hp_1 and Hp_2 are not. Then the 'mean' (AC+DC) solution is still given, but with a variability-flag for the combined magnitude. Finally, one or both of the Hp_1 and Hp_2 are significantly variable (again measured by a normalized amplitude $> t_v$). In this case, the epoch photometry for the individual components may be given, together with the 'mean' (AC) solution for the astrometry. (A further obvious refinement would of course be to continue iterating, solving for the astrometry with the variable photometry fixed, solving again for the photometry with the astrometry fixed, and so on. If time allows, something like this will be implemented for the (few) large-amplitude systems).

Although simple in principle, there have been many problems to solve before the above procedure works in practice. For arbitrary reasons, I made the developments in the SEEKDBL program, but some test runs have been made also for a modified STDDBL. In Table 2 are given some typical fractions of variables, for both known and unknown doubles, as a function of the threshold t_v . Although the normalized amplitude-definitions were somewhat different, I think one may say that the number

of doubles where individual photometric variations for the two components may be discerned is similar (and rather low!) for both known and unknown doubles. The number of variables in combined magnitude is much higher among the 'unknown doubles', however, reflecting probably an uncorrected selection effect where variables are more likely to be tested for duplicity.

Table 2. The percentages of 'variable systems' and 'variable components' as a function of the threshold t_v from sample runs of SEEKDBL (unknown doubles) and STDDBL (known doubles).

t_v	SEEK		STD	
	%(syst)	%(comp)	%(syst)	%(comp)
5	9.9	3.2	3.1	3.4
6	7.4	2.3	2.1	2.1
7	5.9	1.5	1.5	1.5
8	4.5	1.0	1.2	1.1
9	3.7	0.8	0.9	0.8
10	3.0	0.7	0.8	0.6

There are also several cases where both components show large amplitude variations, *but* where the combined magnitude is much more constant. Except for the threshold, one has to check that the combined amplitude is compatible with the individual ones.

6. The new STDDBL and SEEKDBL programs

For 'historical' reasons, I have always used separate programs for 'known' (STDDBL) and 'unknown' (SEEKDBL) doubles. Although I have tried to keep the programs similar, there has always been substantial differences (tied both to different mesh-search strategies and to the use of more complicated weighting and solution-procedures in STDDBL to allow for the 2-pointing systems). After I made most of the above large changes in SEEKDBL, it was thus a laborious task to introduce similar changes in STDDBL. After I got both programs going, I therefore decided to make a serious effort to use more identical (not just very similar) subroutines in both programs. After several weeks of tedious debugging, the programs have now indeed much more in common (some one third of the code exclusive for each program and two thirds in shared subroutines). The 'convergence' may actually be driven much further, but even now I think the maintenance and updating of the programs has been much simplified.

7. Conclusions

The main conclusion from the above tests is that the two main solution programs are now in good shape. Both STDDBL and SEEKDBL have evolved through some 25 numbered versions each since their first use on real data in 1991, and the present ones (9.0) are certainly still not 'final'. There are many 'knobs' to twiddle and many bugs still to be found, but during the evolution I have always been able to compare new versions with old to ensure that the number and reliability of the solutions has been generally increasing. (After the above introduction of AC+DC solutions, there are actually somewhat fewer accepted solutions, but the rejected ones are actually the most unreliable). I feel confident that when run on the new 37-month CHF:s, a realistic set of 'semi-final' double-star solutions will become available within the next month.